

GRAMMAR IS ONE OF THE IMPORTANT PARTS IN LEARNING ENGLISH

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Abstract: this article is devoted to study a language as a part of general knowledge. In the study of language, grammar occupies a central position. But there is also a practical reason to emphasize the study of grammar it is easy to learn to use dictionaries by yourself to find the pronunciation, spelling, or meaning of words, but it is to consult grammar books without a considerable knowledge of grammar.

Keywords: study, general knowledge, affect, understand, practical application, grammar, dictionary, pronunciation, description, phonetic.

Аннотация: данная статья посвящена изучению языка как части общих знаний. В изучении языка грамматика занимает центральное место. Но есть и практическая причина сделать акцент на изучении грамматики: легко научиться самостоятельно пользоваться словарями, чтобы найти произношение, написание или значение слов, но для этого нужно обратиться к учебникам по грамматике без достаточных знаний грамматики.

Ключевые слова: изучение, общие знания, воздействие, понимание, практическое применение, грамматика, словарь, произношение, описание, фонетика.

Annotatsiya: ushbu maqola umumiy bilimlarning bir qismi sifatida tilni o'rganishga bag'ishlangan. Tilni o'rganishda grammatika markaziy o'rinni egallaydi. Ammo grammatikani o'rganishni ta'kidlash uchun amaliy sabab ham bor so'zlarning talaffuzi, imlosi yoki ma'nosini topish uchun o'zingiz lug'atlardan foydalanishni o'rganish oson, ammo grammatika haqida katta ma'lumotga ega bo'lmagan holda grammatika kitoblariga murojaat qilishdir.

Kalit so'zlar: o'rganish, umumiy bilim, ta'sir qilish, tushunish, amaliy qo'llash, grammatika, lug'at, talaffuz, tavsif, fonetik.

The study of language is a part of general knowledge. We study the complex working of the human body to understand ourselves; the same reason should attract us to studying the marvelous complexity of human language.

Everybody has attitudes towards the English language and its varieties, and has opinions on specific features. These attitudes and opinions affect relationships with other people. If you understand the nature of language, you will realize the grounds for your linguistic prejudices and perhaps moderate them; you will also more clearly assess linguistic issues of public concern, such as worries about the state of the language or what to do about the teaching of immigrants. Studying the English language has a more obvious practical application: it can help you to use the language more effectively.

In the study of language, grammar occupies a central position. But there is also a practical reason to emphasize the study of grammar. It is easy to learn to use dictionaries by yourself to find the

pronunciation, spelling, or meanings of words, but it is difficult to consult grammar books without a considerable knowledge of grammar.

There are several applications of grammatical study: (1) A recognition of grammatical structures is often essential for punctuation; (2) A study of one's native grammar is helpful when one studies the grammar of a foreign language; (3) A knowledge of grammar is a help in the interpretation of literary and nonliterary texts, since the interpretation of a passage sometimes depends crucially on grammatical analysis; (4) A study of the grammatical resources of English is useful in composition: in particular, it can help you to evaluate the choices available to you when you come to revise an earlier written draft.

Some combinations of words are possible in English and others are not. As a speaker of English, you can judge that Home computers are now much cheaper is a possible English sentence whereas Home computers now much are cheaper is not, because you know that much is wrongly positioned in the second example. Your ability to recognize such distinctions is evidence that in some sense you know the rules of grammar even if you have never studied a grammar. Similarly, you operate the rules whenever you speak or write (you can put words in the right order) and whenever you interpret what others say (you know that Susan likes Tom means something different from Tom likes Susan But knowing the rules in evaluative and operational senses does not meant you can say what the rules are. You acquire a working knowledge of your native language simply through being exposed to it from early childhood: nobody taught you, for example, where to position much. You study grammar, however, if you want to be able to analyze your language. The analytic grammar makes explicit the knowledge of the rules with which you operate when you use the language. There is a clear difference between the operational grammar and the analytic grammar. After all, many languages have never been analyzed and some have been analyzed only relatively recently. People were speaking and writing English long before the first English grammars appeared at the end of the sixteenth century.

Linguistic communications are channeled mainly through our senses of sound and sight. Grammar is the central component of language. It mediates between the system of sounds or of written symbols, on the one hand, and the system of meaning, on the other. Phonology is the usual term for the sound system in the language: the distinctive sound units and the ways which they may be combined. Orthography parallels phonology in that it deals with the writing system in the language: the distinctive written symbols and their possible combinations. Semantics is concerned with the system of meanings in the language: the meanings of words and the combinatory meanings of larger units.

Three other aspects of language description are often distinguished: phonetics, morphology and pragmatics. Phonetics deals with the physical characteristics of the sounds in the language and how the sounds are produced. Sounds and letters combine to form words or parts of words. Morphology refers to the set of rules that describe the structure of words. The word computer, for example, consists of two parts: the base compute (used separately as a verb) and the suffix -er (found in other nouns derived from verbs, e.g. blender). Pragmatics is concerned with the use of particular utterances within particular situations. For example, Will you join our group? is a question that, depending on the speaker's intention, is a request for information or a request for action.

Certain types of activity have clearly recognized language features; examples include scientific papers, legal documents, sermons, news broadcasts, and fiction. Newspapers have a distinctive

layout, headlines are often highly compressed (Banks warned on student loans), cookery books tend to use many imperatives (Mix the ingredients), labels omit words understood from the object to which they are attached (Shake well).

Some variation depends on the medium, the channel of communication. The major distinction is between spoken and written language. Conversation, the most common type of speech, involves immediate interchange between the participants, who convey their reactions either in words or through facial expressions and bodily movements. There is more spontaneity in conversation than in writing; self-correction occurs in the flow of conversation, whereas it is eliminated through editing in writing. Writing needs to be more explicit, since obscurities and misunderstandings cannot be removed immediately. People feel more committed to what they write because of the potential permanence of the written communication. The differences in the nature of the media is reflected in the greater concision that is possible in writing and in the greater care that writers take over their choice of words.

Language also varies according to the attitude of the speaker or writer towards the listener or reader, towards the topic, and towards the purpose of communication. We can select from features that range from the most formal to the most informal. Comprehend and strive are more formal than their respective equivalents, understand and try. Similarly, This is the student to whom I gave the message is more formal than This is the student I gave the message to. We can end a letter with the casual and friendly Yours ever, the neutral Yours sincerely, or the distant Yours faithfully.

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